

success story

Pilot 2: Sustainable Agriculture National scale

EO based soil monitoring services to support national GHG inventories and CAP

To safeguard natural capital of soils, in a continuously volatile landscape of reduced resources and environmental changes and pave the way for the development of evidence-based conservation recommendations for Common Agricultural Policy, it is essential to improve capacities for soil health monitoring by adopting multidimensional and integrated approaches. However, the available soil maps correspond to a not up-to-date and coarse representation of the various soil properties, making their use impossible for Good Agricultural and Environmental Conditions (GAECs) monitoring in the framework of cross-compliance. Pilot 2 facilitates the access to and integration of national spatial data with untapped GEOSS research-based soil data and different spaceborne sources such as Copernicus, into user's oriented (Lithuanian Paying Agency) applications.

The Soil Data Cube, in its present form, developed by the Interbalkan Environment Center, is providing yearly estimations of soil related indicators (e.g., bare soil frequency, soil organic carbon, clay content) at national scale, exploiting Earth Observation data and deep learning techniques to improve the accuracy of maps, as well as the spatial resolution enabling discrimination at parcel level. The next step will be a hybrid modelling approach, coupling physical process model with the enhanced spatial products and the versatility of data-driven explainable artificial intelligence techniques to quantify SOC sequestration and explore its causality with climate change and management practices in support of eco-schemes.

We look forward to service the National Paying Agencies with these new kinds of information in the post-CAP period, as well as rural sector towards a carbon neutral agriculture.

Useful links:

www.eiffel4climate.eu

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